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The Digital Senegal 2016-2025 Strategy, as an Appropriate Instrument to Implement the Sustainable Development Goals. The Digital Senegal 2016-2025 Strategy

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THE DIGITAL SENEGAL 2016-2025 STRATEGY

In October 2016, Senegal published its national strategy Digital Senegal 2016-2025 (DS2025). This policy docu

ment is well thought, precise, and adapted to the Senegalese context. This strategy is in fact rooted in the previous national development strategy (Senegal Emerging Plan: SEP), adopted by the Government in November 2012, aiming at

being the baseline of every national economic and social policy for the medium and long term. As such, the SEP wants to ensure coherence and focus in policymaking. Through this development plan, the goal of Senegal is to support economic growth with a strong impact on social development and employment. In order to achieve this target, the country must reinforce its achievements in political governance and to focus on economic stability. To implement the national development plan, an important investment program in priority sectors, capable to impulse a strong and continuous growth, has been set in place.

The DS2025 strategy concentrates on one of these priority sectors. In fact, it embodies the Senegalese ambition to maintain its role of leader country in the digital sector at the continental level in Africa and more particularly in West Africa, where the country has always been considered as one of the major economies and one of the preeminent political regimes, known for its stability and development progress since Independence from France in 1960.

The slogan summarizing the digital strategy is: “digital technology available for everyone and for every purpose from 2025 in Senegal together with a dynamic and innovative private sector within an efficient ecosystem”. The total cost of the strategy, including 28 reforms and 69 projects, has been estimated to 1,361 billions of CFA francs (equivalent to 2.3 billions USD)

The strategy is based on three key prerequisites (the legal and institutional framework, human capital, and the digital asset) and four priority areas:

1. An affordable and easy access to digital networks and services
2. An administration serving citizen and enterprises through digital services
3. The support to an innovative digital industry producing value addition
4. The promotion of digital technologies in priority economic sectors.

To understand the DS2025 strategy and its chances to be successfully implemented and to produce the results expected, a clear vision of the economic and political context of Senegal is necessary.

THE ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL CONTEXT IN SENEGAL

Since 1960, Senegal has built a stable and democratic political system, based on free elections and periodic changes in political leadership. Despite some contestations and strikes, since the first election of the president Léopold Senghor, the country has never experienced any political turmoil, despite the changes of power that have taken place since the birth of the contemporary Senegalese state. The last presidential elections in

February 2019, the 11th since Independence, have given a second mandate to the president Macky Sall to continue to implement the SEP for 7 more years. The 2018 Ibrahim Index of African Governance (IIAG), measuring the quality and evolution of political governance in Africa, confirms the Senegalese political stability and the quality of democratic governance.

The IIAG ranks Senegal 10th and points out its steady progress during the last decade in every domain monitored, but more particularly in human

development. According to the IIAG report, Senegal is, together with Uganda, Chad and Capo Verde, among the countries that have registered the most important improvements in relation to access to electricity. If henceforth Senegal is a stable country from a political point of view, according to World Bank data, its economy is also among the top 10 fastest growing economies in 2018.

The country is ranked 8th at the global scale for its real GDP growth at market prices (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Fastest growing economies in 2018 according to their real GDP growth

Enhancing feminine digital entrepreneurship is going to greatly contribute to women empowerment and to social inclusion in the country [Senegal].

Furthermore, this positive economic trend that goes back at least to 2011 is sustainable, as it is rooted in a progressive improvement of the business environment in the country. The annual World Bank Ease of doing business 2020 indicates that Senegal is ranked 123 among 190 economies, constantly improving its performance since 2013, when it was ranked 178. This means that economic growth in Senegal is the result of an entrepreneurial ecosystem constantly improving over time.

Nevertheless, small-scale enterprises constitute 45.8 percent of Senegal's economic private sector, followed by medium-scale enterprises (39.4 percent). This is quite common in sub-Saharan Africa, but it is the sign of a vulnerability of the economy, dominated by small and medium enterprises, for which sustainable financing is still a serious challenge and access to reliable infrastructure and services is problematic. The diagnostic study made under the SEP has pointed out this fragility that the plan aims at resolving (Mansoor et al. 2018), also through the DS2025.

In fact, successful efforts to improve a reliable access to electricity, as indicated by the IIAG, and to enhance Internet connectivity (90 percent of the national territory being already covered by mobile phone connection) are part of the DS2025.

FOCUSING ON DIGITAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

The choice made to focus on digital entrepreneurship is based on the diagnosis made by the strategy that digital enterprises are going to increase the gross domestic product (GDP) by 10 percent by 2025, while creating 35,000 direct jobs. Furthermore, as indicated in the DS2025 (page 20), enhancing feminine digital entrepreneurship is going to greatly contribute to women empowerment and to social inclusion in the country. In fact, the strategy asserts that women's social and economic empowerment through information and communication technologies (ICT) is going to happen by giving access by

2025 to e-commerce and electronic public services to 33 percent of rural women. This is one of the major goals of the strategy.

The choice to focus on women entrepreneurship for the digital sector is based on the fact that women entrepreneurs are numerous and they are a real economic strength for the country. Women entrepreneurship has been encouraged and developed in the last decades through various development policies and projects funded through development assistance schemes, as a tool to enhance women empowerment in the country. As a matter of fact, women entrepreneurs are an important and ever growing reality in Senegal, despite the difficulties and the fact that most of their enterprises are small and financially fragile. In this context, women entrepreneurship is a “necessity”, but also a powerful social and economic game changer for the country. A number of recent initiatives have been developed in recent years to support women

entrepreneurship in Senegal: the Réseau des jeunes femmes entrepreneures and the Maison des femmes entrepreneures, both created in 2018. The existence of an [Association des femmes sénégalaises dans les TIC](#) also indicates that women entrepreneurs in the ICT are an important reality in the country, from which the strategy wants to take advantage.

DS2025: A TOOL TO IMPLEMENT THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS, WITH A FOCUS ON EDUCATION

The DS2025 strategy clearly indicates that its implementation is in line with the priority areas of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), especially when it comes to gender equality and environmental protection. The strategy states that digital technologies, especially the Internet of things (IoT) applications and machine-to-machine (M2M) communications radically transform service provision and subsequently contribute to SDGs progress.

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It is henceforth critical to transform the entire educational system (from primary education to tertiary and professional education) in line with the development and widespread use of digital technologies. To this extent, the Ministry in charge of education is reforming school programs. It is also introducing digital knowledge and information at every level of the educational system. The Ministry of tertiary education is also implementing relevant projects, including: an integrated governance system for higher education (SIGESR) and the Virtual University of Senegal. The country aims at developing distance learning and virtual platforms to attract foreign students and improve the quality of its university system. Other actions focus on modernizing school management and governance through digital technologies and training school teachers and professor to digital technologies.

Nevertheless, to achieve the goal to give access to a computer to every student and to connect to the Internet and equip 50 percent of the schools and 100 percent of the universities by 2025, according to the aim of the

strategy, lots remains to be done, especially in terms of capacities to be built.

CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The Senegalese example demonstrate the importance of having a strong national development plan, like the SEP, taking into account the resources available in the country, pointing out major gaps and deficiencies, setting out clear and realistic goals, indicating priority economic domains and opening the way to sectoral public policies to implement the plan within a precise timeline and budget. Furthermore, the national voluntary review of the SDGs realized by Senegal in 2018 (Republic of Senegal 2018) proves that the SEP is perfectly in line with the SDGs that it implements in the specific context of Senegal.

The DS2025 strategy emphasizes the critical importance of digitalization, to structurally and sustainably transform the economy and implement the SDGs.

If this is true for a developing country like Senegal, the same applies to Gulf countries still overrelying on extractive resources and still struggling to really diversify their economies, while focusing on SDGs implementation and sustainable development. Qatar E-government 2020 Strategy is for example similar to the DS2025, but it only concentrates on digital government, while the Senegalese strategy encompasses various key economic sectors (mainly agriculture, health, and education) and more precisely priority economic domains.

To this extent, the Senegalese digital strategy contributes to build productive and human capacities and a strong emphasis is given to capacity development in the DS2025, pointing out that digitalization is a critical tool to build individual and economic capacities for a country. This points out the important role of education and even more of digital education for job creation and also for implementing the SDGs through SDG8.

To conclude, the Senegalese strategy includes a precise budget and financing mechanism, indicating that 73 percent of the budget must come from the private sector, 17 percent from the public sector and 10 percent from public private partnerships (PPPs). This issue brief recommends that ad hoc policies must be set in place to ensure that the budget is available and that every stakeholder does its part, which has not to be given for granted.

The major policy recommendation that this issue brief wants to highlight is that policies, financing mechanism, political will, the educational system, and the business environment must to converge towards a common goal, which must be considered as a common and superior interest (SDGs implementation) and converging efforts must be set in place to achieve this goal. Digitalization is a critical instrument to this extent: it creates unique opportunities for individuals, societies and economics.

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